

Corrosion inhibitory effects of some Mannich bases on mild steel in acid media

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Abstract : Weight loss and potentiometric methods have been used to study the corrosion inhibition of mild steel in acidic solution (HCl and H₂SO₄) by four newly synthesised Mannich bases viz. 3-oxo-3-phenyl-*N,N*-dimethyl propanamine hydrochloride (MB₁), 3,5-dioxo-5-phenyl-*N,N*-dimethyl pentanamine hydrochloride (MB₂), 2,2-dimethyl-3-oxo-*N,N*-dimethyl butanamine hydrochloride (MB₃) and 3-oxo-*N,N*-dimethyl butanamine hydrochloride (MB₄). Corrosion inhibition efficiency have been found to depend upon the concentration of inhibitor as well as that of acid. Inhibition efficiency increases with increasing concentration of inhibitor and decreases with increasing concentration of acid. Inhibition efficiency is more in HCl than in H₂SO₄. Inhibition efficiency was found maximum upto 92.79% in HCl solution whereas it is 75.65% in H₂SO₄.

Keywords : Corrosion, inhibition efficiency, Mannich bases, weight loss, potential, surface coverage.

Introduction

Many organic compounds in addition to natural products have been used to prevent the corrosion of mild steel in acidic media^{1,2}. These compounds adsorb on metal surface and form a barrier to oxygen and moisture by complexing with metal ions or by removing corrodants from the environment, thus inhibit the corrosion. Some of the inhibitors facilitate formation of passivating film on the metal surface³.

Generally the organic compounds containing heteroatoms like O, N, S are found to work as effective corrosion inhibitor⁴⁻⁷. The efficiency of these compounds depends on the electron density around the heteroatom⁸. Heteroatoms such as O, N and S are capable of forming coordinate covalent bond with metal owing to their free electron pairs. Inhibition efficiency also depends upon the number of adsorption active centres in the molecule, their charge density, molecular size, mode of adsorption and formation of metallic complexes⁹.

Corrosion of mild steel and its alloys in different acid media have been studied^{10,11}. Some workers have studied corrosion inhibition efficiency of Mannich bases for mild steel in acid media^{12,13}. Present investigation deals with the synthesis of Mannich bases and study them

as corrosion inhibitor.

Experimental

Mannich bases were synthesised by conventional methods i.e. by refluxing equimolar quantities of ethanolic solutions of corresponding ketones, formaldehyde and secondary amines in a round bottom flask for about 4-5 h and then adding some acetone in it and mixture was left in a refrigerator overnight. Resulting crystals were filtered and then recrystallized by acetone which were then dried and collected in pure state.

Rectangular specimens of mild steel of dimension 2.0 × 2.0 × 0.03 cm containing a small hole of about 1 mm diameter near the upper edge were used for studying the corrosion rate. Specimens were cleaned by buffing to produce a mirror finish and were then degreased. Initial weight of specimens were taken upto the three decimal of gm with a digital balance. The solutions of HCl were prepared using double distilled water. All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Each specimen was suspended by a V-shaped glass hook made up of capillary tube in a beaker containing 50 mL of the test solution at 25 ± 0.1 °C. After the sufficient exposure, specimen was cleaned by running water

and then dried by hot air dryer then final weight was taken. Duplicate experiments were performed in each case and mean values of the weight loss were determined.

The percentage inhibition efficiency ($\eta\%$) was calculated as¹⁴

$$\eta\% = \frac{100(\Delta W_u - \Delta W_i)}{\Delta W_u}$$

where ΔW_u and ΔW_i are the weight loss of metal in uninhibited and in inhibited solution respectively. The degree of surface coverage (θ) of specimen by inhibitor can be calculated as¹⁵

$$\theta = \frac{(\Delta W_u - \Delta W_i)}{\Delta W_u}$$

Potentiometric studies were also performed for the same specimen. In this study potential of test solutions were recorded at regular intervals using high precision millivoltmeter cum pH meter during the exposure of specimen in corrosive acidic media with and without inhibitor.

Results and discussion

Weight loss, percentage inhibition efficiencies and surface coverage for different concentrations of HCl and H₂SO₄ are given in Tables 1 and 2. It can be seen from both the tables that inhibition efficiency increases with increasing concentration of inhibitor but decreases with

Table 1. Weight loss and percentage inhibition efficiency ($\eta\%$) for mild steel in HCl solution with given inhibitor addition at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$

Concn. of inhibitor (ppm)	Area of specimen : 8 cm ²											
	0.5 N HCl (120 h)			1 N HCl (96 h)			1.5 N HCl (70 h)			2 N HCl (48 h)		
	Δw (g)	$\eta\%$	$\log \theta/(1 - \theta)$	Δw (g)	$\eta\%$	$\log \theta/(1 - \theta)$	Δw (g)	$\eta\%$	$\log \theta/(1 - \theta)$	Δw (g)	$\eta\%$	$\log \theta/(1 - \theta)$
Uninhibited	0.722	-	-	0.653	-	-	0.600	-	-	0.663	-	-
MB ₁ :												
100	0.210	70.91	0.3869	0.220	66.30	0.2938	0.221	63.16	0.2341	0.262	60.48	0.1847
200	0.201	72.16	0.4136	0.208	68.14	0.3301	0.210	65.00	0.2688	0.250	62.29	0.2179
300	0.185	74.37	0.4626	0.195	70.44	0.3771	0.198	67.00	0.3075	0.235	64.55	0.2602
400	0.172	76.17	0.5046	0.182	72.12	0.4127	0.182	69.66	0.3609	0.218	67.11	0.3097
MB ₂ :												
100	0.175	75.76	0.4949	0.205	68.60	0.3393	0.202	66.33	0.2944	0.240	63.80	0.2461
200	0.160	77.83	0.5453	0.192	70.59	0.3802	0.190	68.33	0.3339	0.229	65.46	0.2776
300	0.125	82.68	0.6788	0.180	72.43	0.4194	0.162	73.00	0.4319	0.210	68.32	0.3337
400	0.052	92.79	1.1092	0.162	75.19	0.4815	0.150	75.00	0.4771	0.198	70.13	0.3706

Table-1 (contd.)

MB ₃ :												
100	0.225	68.83	0.3440	0.235	64.01	0.2500	0.223	62.83	0.2279	0.272	58.97	0.1575
200	0.218	69.80	0.3638	0.223	65.84	0.2849	0.218	63.66	0.2434	0.262	60.48	0.1847
300	0.205	71.60	0.4015	0.210	67.84	0.3241	0.206	65.66	0.2814	0.250	62.29	0.2179
400	0.195	72.99	0.4316	0.202	69.06	0.3486	0.195	67.50	0.3174	0.239	63.95	0.2489
MB ₄ :												
100	0.260	63.98	0.2494	0.250	61.71	0.2072	0.242	59.66	0.1699	0.287	56.71	0.1172
200	0.240	66.75	0.1026	0.238	63.55	0.2413	0.234	61.00	0.1942	0.268	59.57	0.1683
300	0.232	67.86	0.3245	0.226	65.39	0.2763	0.225	62.50	0.2218	0.256	61.38	0.2012
400	0.225	68.83	0.3440	0.213	67.38	0.3150	0.212	64.66	0.2623	0.245	62.44	0.2207

Table 2. Weight loss and percentage inhibition efficiency ($\eta\%$) for mild steel in H₂SO₄ solution with given inhibitor addition at 25 ± 0.1 °C

Concn. of inhibitor (ppm)	Area of specimen : 8 cm ²											
	0.5 N H ₂ SO ₄ (48 h)			1 N H ₂ SO ₄ (25 h)			1.5 N H ₂ SO ₄ (22 h)			2 N H ₂ SO ₄ (20 h)		
	Δw (g)	$\eta\%$	$\log \theta/(1 - \theta)$	Δw (g)	$\eta\%$	$\log \theta/(1 - \theta)$	Δw (g)	$\eta\%$	$\log \theta/(1 - \theta)$	Δw (g)	$\eta\%$	$\log \theta/(1 - \theta)$
Uninhibited	0.768	-	-	0.703	-	-	0.682	-	-	0.758	-	-
MB ₁ :												
100	0.240	68.75	0.3424	0.258	63.30	0.2367	0.270	60.41	0.1834	0.310	59.10	0.1598
200	0.232	69.79	0.3636	0.240	65.86	0.2853	0.258	62.17	0.2157	0.295	61.08	0.1957
300	0.225	70.70	0.3825	0.232	66.99	0.3073	0.245	64.07	0.2511	0.282	62.79	0.2272
400	0.205	73.30	0.4385	0.216	69.27	0.3529	0.225	67.06	0.3087	0.260	65.69	0.2820
MB ₂ :												
100	0.228	70.31	0.3744	0.242	65.57	0.2797	0.252	63.04	0.2318	0.290	61.74	0.2077
200	0.215	72.00	0.4101	0.232	67.21	0.3130	0.238	65.10	0.2707	0.278	63.32	0.2370
300	0.200	73.95	0.4531	0.218	68.99	0.3472	0.227	66.71	0.3018	0.270	64.37	0.2568
400	0.187	75.65	0.4922	0.203	71.12	0.3913	0.210	69.20	0.3515	0.252	66.75	0.3026
MB ₃ :												
100	0.255	66.79	0.3034	0.265	62.30	0.2181	0.275	59.67	0.1701	0.315	58.44	0.1480
200	0.242	68.48	0.3369	0.250	64.43	0.2579	0.265	61.14	0.1968	0.308	59.36	0.1645
300	0.235	69.40	0.3556	0.238	66.14	0.2907	0.252	63.04	0.2318	0.297	60.81	0.1907
400	0.220	71.35	0.3962	0.223	68.27	0.3327	0.230	66.27	0.2932	0.282	62.79	0.2272
MB ₄ :												
100	0.270	64.84	0.2657	0.285	59.45	0.1661	0.287	57.91	0.1385	0.335	55.80	0.1011
200	0.256	66.66	0.3008	0.272	61.30	0.1997	0.270	60.41	0.1834	0.320	57.78	0.1362
300	0.247	67.83	0.3239	0.250	64.43	0.2579	0.258	62.17	0.2163	0.312	58.83	0.1550
400	0.232	69.79	0.3636	0.228	67.56	0.3186	0.242	64.51	0.2594	0.300	60.42	0.1836

increasing concentration of acid and all the inhibitors show maximum efficiency in 0.5 N HCl and in 0.5 N H₂SO₄. The maximum efficiency was obtained for MB₂ at an inhibitor concentration of 400 ppm in 0.5 N HCl and in 0.5 N H₂SO₄ i.e. 92.79% and 75.65% respectively. These results show that Mannich bases show more inhibition efficiency in HCl than in H₂SO₄. Variation of inhibition efficiency with concentration of inhibitor is depicted graphically in Fig. 1 for HCl and in Fig. 2 for H₂SO₄.

Maximum efficiency shown by MB₂ in both HCl and in H₂SO₄ is due to the more number of atoms having high electron density which is responsible for more adsorption of inhibitor on the metal surface and decreases the rate of reaction.

The variation of electrode potential of different test solution were also taken into account with and without inhibitor. The observed variation of potential with time for MB₂ in 0.5 N HCl and in 0.5 N H₂SO₄ are shown in

Fig. 1. Variation of inhibition efficiency with concentration of inhibitor for mild steel in 0.5 N HCl.

Fig. 2. Variation of inhibition efficiency with concentration of inhibitor for mild steel in 0.5 N H₂SO₄.

Fig. 3. Variation of potential with time for mild steel in 1 N HCl for MB₁.

Fig. 4. Variation of potential with time for mild steel in 1 N H₂SO₄ for MB₁.

covered by inhibitors so electrochemical reactions decrease due to which the electrode potential does not vary as sharp as in initial stage.

Adsorption plays an important role in the inhibition of metallic corrosion by organic inhibitors. The efficiencies of inhibitors expressed as the relative reduction in corrosion rate can be qualitatively related to the amount of adsorbed inhibitors on the metal surface. It is assumed that the corrosion reactions are prevented from occurring over the active sites of the metal surface covered by adsorbed inhibitor species, whereas the corrosion reaction occurs normally on the surface at inhibitor free area. The inhibition efficiency is directly proportional to the fraction of the surface covered with adsorbed inhibitors. The higher ionisation of Mannich bases in HCl than in H₂SO₄ may be the reason of these compounds exhibiting higher inhibition efficiency in HCl as compared in H₂SO₄ because increased ionisation of inhibitor molecule will facilitate the adsorption of inhibitor on the mild steel surface. Hoar and Holliday¹⁶ exhibited that the Langmuir adsorption isotherm

$$\log \left[\frac{\theta}{1 - \theta} \right] = \log A + \log C - \frac{Q}{2.303 RT}$$

should give a straight line of unit gradient for the plot of $\log \left[\frac{\theta}{1 - \theta} \right]$ versus $\log C$, where A is a temperature independent constant, C is the bulk concentration of the inhibitor and Q is the heat liberated in electrochemical reaction. The corresponding plots shown in Fig. 5 for HCl and in Fig. 6 for H₂SO₄ are linear but the gradient is not unity. This deviation can be explained on the basis of interaction among the adsorbed species on the metal surface.

Figs. 3 and 4 respectively. It is clear from both the figures that there is an increase in the electrode potential initially. But after sometime the electrode potential hardly increases or becomes almost constant. The probable reason may be attributed to the fact that initially the electrochemical reactions occurring on the surface are fast due to presence of active sites so there is a rise in electrode potential with time. After sometime the active sites are

Fig. 5. Langmuir adsorption isotherm for mild steel in 0.5 N HCl.

Fig. 6. Langmuir adsorption isotherm for mild steel in 0.5 N H₂SO₄.

Conclusion :

A study of four newly synthesized Mannich bases viz. 3-oxo-3-phenyl-*N,N*-dimethyl propanamine hydrochloride (MB₁), 3,5-dioxo-5-phenyl-*N,N*-dimethyl pentanamine hydrochloride (MB₂), 2,2-dimethyl-3-oxo-*N,N*-dimethyl butanamine hydrochloride (MB₃) and 3-oxo-*N,N*-dimethyl butanamine hydrochloride (MB₄) has shown them to be effective inhibitors for the corrosion of mild steel in HCl and in H₂SO₄ solutions. Weight loss has shown that the inhibition efficiency of Mannich bases increases with increasing concentration of inhibitor but decreases with increasing concentration of acid. Synthesised Mannich bases are more effective in HCl than in H₂SO₄ solution.

It has been observed that Langmuir adsorption isotherm deviates from its ideal behaviour due to the interaction between the adsorbed species.

MB₂ has shown highest inhibition efficiency i.e.

92.79% at the highest inhibitor concentration (400 ppm) in 0.5 N HCl solution.

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